

Review Article

Innovations In Diuretic Treatment: A Promising Solution For Chronic Diseases

Jaya Mehetre*, Kiran Dhamak, Kalpana Sable, Trupti Bhalekar

Department of Quality Assurance, PRES College of Pharmacy (Women's), Chincholi, Nashik-422102.

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ABSTRACT

Diuretics are at the centre of the ongoing debate about which medications should be used to start a hypertension treatment programme. One of the biggest issues is sorting out actual class specific effects, such as differentiating true class-specific effects of diuretics from those of beta blockers, because the majority of important studies contain sophisticated treatment algorithms and allow various background treatments. In placebo-controlled clinical investigations, thiazide diuretics were the first effective antihypertensive medications that were well tolerated and considerably decreased cardiovascular morbidity and death. Even yet, these medications are still regarded as essential therapeutic tools for the management of hypertension patients. A brief discussion of the treatment of resistant edoema and the use of diuretics in non-edematous states, such as essential hypertension and other conditions, is followed by a description of the successful use of diuretics in specific edematous states, such as congestive heart failure, chronic renal failure, nephrotic syndrome, and liver disease. Analysed are the components necessary to successfully induce enough natriuresis in such circumstances. The prevention and management of these side effects of diuretic medication are also discussed since attaining diuresis may induce substantial hypokalemia, hyponatremia, metabolic alkalosis, and worsening prerenal azotemia. Congestive heart failure, edoema, cirrhosis, bodybuilding, autism, toxemia, and poisoning (forced diuresis) are some of the words that are important to know.

INTRODUCTION

The selection of medications to begin therapy has been one of the most divisive issues in the management of hypertension during the past 20 years. The patient with simple hypertension who lacks strong indications for any specific

medication class is especially at risk for this. The role of diuretics, which have at various periods and by various authorities been favoured, avoided, or viewed as a comparable choice, in comparison to other pharmacological groups, has been at the

*Corresponding Author: Jaya Mehetre

Address: Department of Quality Assurance, PRES College of Pharmacy (Women's), Chincholi, Nashik-422102

Email ✉: jayamehetre2019@gmail.com

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centre of this controversy [1–14]. Thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics are essential for treating hypertension, but whether they should be used as first- or second-line medications is a contentious topic. Thiazide diuretics are advised to be considered as suitable as b-blockers, calcium antagonists, ACE inhibitors, and angiotensin receptor blockers for the initiation and maintenance of antihypertensive treatment, according to the European Society of Cardiology/European Society of Hypertension (ESC/ESH) guidelines [15]. Thiazide diuretics should be preferred medications in "most" hypertensive patients, either alone or in combination with medications from other classes, according to the Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee (JNC VII) on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure [16]. It has been demonstrated that lowering blood pressure (BP) lowers the risk of CV morbidity and death. The risk of stroke and heart failure (HF) is decreased, which is the major advantage of reducing blood pressure. Antihypertensive medication was diuretic-based in numerous trials where a decrease in cardiovascular events was reported [17–22]. Diuretics are at the centre of the ongoing debate about which medications should be used to start a hypertension treatment programme. One of the biggest issues is sorting out actual class specific effects, such as differentiating true class-specific effects of diuretics from those of beta blockers, because the majority of important studies contain sophisticated treatment algorithms and allow various background treatments. Despite these challenges, the data support the fact that diuretics are at least as effective as the more recent first-line treatment options in avoiding cardiovascular events. The key area of uncertainty is to the risk of metabolic outcomes, such as new-onset diabetes, and renal outcomes. Here, the data shows that renin-angiotensin system inhibitors may offer

more protection than the other pharmacological types. The most recent international recommendations take into account these difficulties and list diuretics among the first-line medications for the treatment of hypertension; however they do differ regarding the function of diuretics in the start of therapy [23].

Era where diuretics are being used therapeutically as Antihypertensive Drug

When diuretics were first launched in the 1960s, they were mostly used as a supplement to stronger medications like adrenergic agents or hydralazine, which were used to treat mild to severe hypertension. [24] By the 1970s, beta blockers were well-accepted, and treatment was expanded to lower grades of hypertension using "step therapy," a course of action that involved starting with a diuretic, adding a beta blocker if necessary, and finally a vasodilator, often hydralazine. The publication of the groundbreaking meta-analysis by Collins et al. [25] revealed that the anticipated reductions in stroke were achieved, but that the reduction in myocardial infarction was disappointing, being much less than predicted by the major observational studies [26]. This coincided with the availability of new classes of blood pressure-lowering medications, the ACEI, the CCB, and the alpha blockers. Many believed that the well-known metabolic side-effects of diuretics, such as hypokalemia, dyslipidemia, and glucose intolerance, may be to blame. Due to the general notion that a single pharmacological therapy would be effective and efficient, newer medicines gained favour throughout the 1980s, step therapy was abandoned, and the age of monotherapy was inaugurated.[24] Despite its metabolic adverse effects, diuretics were found to be highly beneficial in preventing both stroke and coronary heart disease in three large studies conducted on older patients and published in 1991 and 1992. [27] These data, together with the dearth of clinical trials showing that ACEI or CCB might

prevent these severe end points, caused diuretics and beta blockers to regain their prior dominance. As a result, diuretics were once again approved as first-line medications by all authorities in the 1990s, with the general consensus being that they were particularly useful in the elderly. [4, 9,10,28]. The medication is now being extended to "normotensive" patients who have a high risk of cardiovascular events, such as those who have diabetes, established coronary disease, or established cerebrovascular illness, renal disease, or any of the other conditions listed above. The majority of patients who need blood pressure-lowering medications today, according to all experts, require combined treatment with diuretics. All recommendations concur that diuretics are among the first-line classes of medications and that they can be used to start a therapy, but they disagree on where they should fall in the hierarchy. The stages of a diuretic are outlined below.

Table: 1. Phases in the use of Diuretics [29]

In 1960s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADJUNCT to more potent drugs • Moderate and severe hypertension
In 1970s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First step in STEP THERAPY • Included in most major trials
In 1980s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transition to MONOTHERAPY • Metabolic effects: fall from grace
In 1990s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Line drugs • Vindicated by SHEP, STOP, MRC
21st Century	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More controversy: ALLHAT versus ANBP2 and ASCOT • Cardiovascular versus Metabolic Outcomes

ALLHAT: Antihypertensive and Lipid-Lowering Treatment to Prevent Heart Attack Trial

ANBP2: Australian National Blood Pressure Study

ASCOT: Anglo-Scandinavian Cardiac Outcomes Trial

SHEP: Systolic Hypertension in the Elderly Program

MRC: Medical Research Council

CCB: Calcium Channel Blocker

ACE: Angiotensin Convertase Enzymes

CV: Cardio Vascular

HF: Heart Failure

BP: Blood Pressure

JNC: Joint National Committee

ESC/ESH: European Society of Cardiology/ European Society of Hypertension

STOP: Swedish Trial in Old Patients with Hypertension

Specific situations and indications for diuretics [23]

The main recommendations specify a number of particular scenarios as "compelling indications" for the use of diuretics as blood pressure-lowering medications. These consist of:

1. Systolic hypertension in elderly people.
2. at least those of African descent who are black.
3. subjects who already have established cerebrovascular illness and who also take ACEI.
4. those who have ventricular dysfunction or heart failure.
5. Patients at high risk of developing new diabetes should not use diuretics.

- IGT, or impaired glucose tolerance
- Reduced IFG (fasting blood sugar)
- Being under 60 years old and overweight
- Metabolic disorder

Uses of diuretics other than antihypertensive drugs Diuretics use in Cirrhosis

According to the Merck Manual, cirrhosis—the third-leading cause of mortality in the US—describes a chronic liver disease marked by the accumulation of scar tissue. Long-term cirrhosis development frequently goes unnoticed until issues emerge. Since cirrhosis cannot be cured, therapy focuses on reducing symptoms brought on by complications and slowing the disease's course. Diuretics, sometimes known as water pills, remove

extra fluid, making them effective for addressing a number of cirrhosis-related problems. According to the Lucile Packard Children's Hospital at Stanford, blood enters the liver through the intestines and stomach, allowing the liver to contain around 13 percent of the total amount of blood at any given moment. Blood flow becomes restricted in the liver as scar tissue accumulates. The portal vein, which is the conduit that delivers blood from the digestive system to the liver, has a rise in pressure as a result. Through a condition called portal hypertension, blood is diverted into the tiny blood arteries that surround the liver, which causes an accumulation of fluid in the body. The term "ascites" refers to the buildup of fluid inside the abdominal cavity. The body releases vasodilators, which are chemicals like vasopressin that assist relax blood arteries, when blood pressure in and around the liver increases. Although vasopressin, an antidiuretic, causes the body to retain more salt and water, it also helps to alleviate portal hypertension by relaxing the blood arteries. The extra water raises the blood volume, which is what ultimately causes the elevated portal blood pressure. The fluid leaks from the blood vessels as a result of the pressure and gathers in the abdominal cavity [30]. There are several varieties of diuretics, and each one inhibits salt reabsorption in various locations along the tubes inside the kidneys. Spirolactone, a potassium-sparing diuretic, is a medication that doctors frequently use to manage the side effects of cirrhosis. A loop diuretic called furosemide can help Spirolactone work better, but on its own, it doesn't do anything for cirrhosis. The efficacy of diuretics in the treatment of cirrhosis is increased by consuming a low-sodium diet.

Diuretics use in Edema

The body's blood flow is impacted by the elevated blood pressure surrounding its tissues. The tiny capillaries in the legs may leak fluid due to portal hypertension. The body responds to the capillaries'

fluid leakage by retaining more salt and water, which helps to maintain a consistent blood volume. According to MayoClinic.com, this actually makes capillaries leak more, enabling fluid to accumulate in the surrounding tissues. Edoema is the medical term for the swelling of tissues brought on by the buildup of fluid. The kidneys filter blood to eliminate wastes and maintain a balanced amount of water and salts in the body. The kidneys are made up of millions of microscopic capillaries. Although the kidneys eliminate salt, primarily sodium, the body absorbs a large portion of it as the fluids flow through the kidneys' network of tubes. Cardiovascular Pharmacology Concepts states that diuretics prevent the reabsorption of sodium and that each molecule of sodium taken from the blood draws a molecule of water. Diuretics aid in the relief of both ascites and edoema by eliminating extra water from the body³⁰. Heart failure, cirrhosis, the nephrotic syndrome, and renal failure are just a few of the conditions that can cause generalised edoema; when severe, the extra fluid buildup is known as anasarca. The combination of dietary salt restriction and diuretic therapy typically with a loop diuretic works well for edematous individuals. But some people are resistive to this treatment plan. Inadequate diuretic dose or frequency, excessive sodium intake, delayed intestinal absorption of oral diuretics, decreased diuretic excretion into the urine, and increased sodium reabsorption at sites in the nephron other than those inhibited by the diuretic are just a few of the causes of persistent fluid retention that can be identified [31–34]. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (NSAIDs) may make the body less susceptible to the diuretic effects of vasodilator and natriuretic prostaglandins. In edematous individuals, these agents should be stopped if at all possible [35]. Furosemide, bumetanide, and torsemide are three examples of the sulfonamide-based loop diuretics that are

commonly used to treat edematous patients. Because it can be more ototoxic than sulfonamide diuretics in large doses and is difficult to deliver intravenously due to its relative insolubility, ethacrynic acid, which is not a sulfonamide, is rarely used. Patients who are allergic to sulfonamide-based diuretics, particularly thiazide diuretics, should utilise ethacrynic acid as a treatment option. There is very little proof that sulfonamide antimicrobials and non-antimicrobials can cause allergic cross-reactivity. Therefore, it would be predicted that people who have a history of sulfonamide allergy to antimicrobial medications might tolerate non-antimicrobial sulfonamides like loop diuretics. When allergic responses do happen, they seem to be caused more by a tendency to have allergies than by sulfonamide cross-reactivity [36].

Diuretic in Preeclampsia, Pregnancy induced hypertension, Toxemia

Preeclampsia is characterised by the development of protein in the urine (albuminuria, proteinuria) after the 20th week of pregnancy [37], along with high blood pressure, hypertension, swelling, and edoema. Preeclampsia can range in intensity from moderate to severe; the mild variety is commonly referred to as gestational hypertension caused by proteinuria or pregnancy-induced proteinuric hypertension [38]. Swelling of the face and hands, vision problems, headaches, and high blood pressure are among the symptoms that commonly start to manifest after the 20th week of pregnancy. The signs of severe preeclampsia are more noticeable. There might also be jaundice. If untreated, severe preeclampsia might result in eclampsia, which could kill the mother and fetus [39]. Similar to eclampsia, severe preeclampsia calls for hospitalisation and is a medical emergency. [40,41]. Prescription drugs to lower blood pressure (hypertension) may be used when mild preeclampsia becomes a major hazard to the mother's health, but they are not advised for mild

preeclampsia. To treat severe pregnancy-induced hypertension that causes pulmonary edoema and congestive heart failure, doctors prescribe medications known as diuretics. Agents used include the thiazide diuretics Hydrochlorothiazide (HydroDIURIL), Indapamide (Lozol), and Metolazone (Zaroxolyn); Loop Diuretics including Furosemide (Lasix), Bumetanide (Bumex), and Torsemide (Demadex); and potassium-sparing diuretics, such as Spironolactone (Aldactone), Triamteren (Dyazide, Maxzide), and Amilorides (Midamor). Diuretics may be combined with beta-blockers, such as Propranolol (Inderal), Metoprolol (Lopressor, Toprol XL), Atenolol (Tenormin), Carvedilol (Coreg), labetalol (Normodyne) and Bisoprolol (Zebeta), or ACE inhibitors, including Captopril (Capoten), Benazepril (Lotensin), Lisinopril (Zestril, Prinivil), Enalapril (Vasotec), and Quinapril (Accupril). Calcium channel blockers can also be used to treat high blood pressure. Examples include Amlodipine (Norvasc), Verapamil (Calan SR, Verelan PM), Nifedipin (Adalat CC, Procardia), and Diltiazem (Cardizem CD). Pregnant women with severe preeclampsia are frequently administered the peripheral vasodilator hyralazine.

Diuretics use in Congestive heart failure

The main objectives of therapy for a patient with heart failure are symptom alleviation and prognosis improvement. The diuretics are therapeutically superior in their ability to treat clinical symptoms and signs of heart failure compared to all other anti-heart failure medications now on the market. All diuretics, whether given intravenously or orally, provide a significant decrease in the elevated pulmonary vascular pressures along with a little drop in cardiac output [48]. Diuretics, especially if given in large dosages, promote the release of renin, which then activates the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone pathway. However, their quantitative

effect on the neuroendocrine profile at various stages of heart failure is yet unknown. Diuretics lower plasma catecholamine levels in patients with moderate heart failure, but their sympatholytic effects in more severe instances and their effects on the metabolically active organs in these individuals remain unknown [37]. Segmental nephron blockage, which concurrently blocks sodium reabsorption in the proximal tubule, the loop of Henle, the distal tubule, and the collecting duct, is a method for overcoming diuretic resistance. Breathlessness feelings and peripheral edoema symptoms are improved by diuretics in congestive heart failure patients in direct proportion to the induced diuresis. These advantages are typically linked to a considerable increase in patients' perceptions of their quality of life and financial stability. Chronic diuretic medication has few side effects, although blood electrolyte levels should be checked for hypokalemia and hypomagnesemia. Although it is uncertain how diuretics affect congestive heart failure patients' prognoses, they have been a key component of all the treatments used in survival studies that also included beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, and vasodilators. Diuretics are the most affordable medication class now available for the treatment of individuals with congestive heart failure⁴², in addition to their therapeutic advantages.

Diuretics use in Poisoning

In medicine, loop diuretics are used to treat edoema, excessive blood pressure, and blood poisoning by clearing the blood of poisons and foreign substances. The rate of salicylate excretion may be accelerated by an intravenous mannitol infusion, either through an increase in urine output or by a mannitol-specific action. Forced alkaline diuresis is a well-established method for treating salicylate poisoning, but its role in producing the diuresis is less clear [43].

Diuretics use in Body building

The great majority of hospitalisations and fatalities in the bodybuilding industry are due to loop diuretics, which are by far the most frequently utilised diuretics. The most popular loop diuretic is definitely furosimide (marketed as Lasix), which is affordable and widely accessible. Another non-discriminatory diuretic that acts directly on the kidneys, loop diuretics eliminate all fluids that pass through the kidneys. As they essentially drain potassium, sodium, and calcium from the body with every fluid that enters, they have a significant impact on the electrolyte balance. A reduction in blood pressure, thickening of the blood from a lack of fluids, dizziness, renal failure, severe cramping from electrolyte imbalances, and even death from heart muscle cramping are all possible side effects. Given the drug's tremendous potency and the various water loss strategies used by bodybuilders to prepare for competitions, it doesn't take much Lasix to have severely negative health effects [44]. When training for bodybuilding competitions, athletes want to look as hard and chiselled as they can. This entails growing muscle over a period of months or years, followed by a period of time during which a limited diet and aerobic exercise are performed in an effort to reduce body fat to the lowest level feasible in order to highlight the full definition of the muscle. There are several techniques to help the body lose water as you get ready for a competition. Most of the time, all of these techniques are used. Cardiovascular exercise while wearing heavy clothing, eliminating sodium from the diet, excessive water intake followed by a sudden and drastic reduction in water intake, drinking distilled water devoid of minerals and electrolytes, herbs, and naturally occurring water-reducers, and, most importantly, the use of pharmaceutical diuretics are some of these methods. Since they aim to upset the body's normal equilibrium of fluid and electrolyte balance and can disturb several bodily functions, they are all potentially harmful to some extent. But the

body is an expert at maintaining a healthy balance. It can adjust itself in most instances to this by adjusting electrolyte balances and holding on to just enough fluids to keep functioning properly. However, diuretic medications are strong enough to overcome the body's defences and wreck havoc within the body. Recent scientific research and analysis has greatly enhanced herbal and natural water-loss methods. Now, it is possible to lower water to the desired amount without endangering one's health or life. Hydradry by Allmax Nutrition is a cutting-edge example of one of these products that is brand-new for 2011. A 14-Day water loss programme called Hydradry was created especially for pre-contest weight loss. Nine different potent plant extracts, including two types of taraxacum, which is taken from the dandelion plant, are used in a three-stage water depletion technique. Quick and efficient water loss through Hydradry is equivalent to that of many other treatments combined. Additionally, to maintain these levels in the body at a constant level, Hydradry is supplemented with a scientifically balanced combination of B6, calcium, magnesium, and potassium [44]. Numerous other negative side effects of diuretics might force its termination. Although its effect is currently less noticeable than in the past due to the widespread use of low-dose thiazides, potassium-sparing diuretics, and combinations with ACE inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers, hypokalemia was proposed as a possible cause of arrhythmias and sudden cardiac death [30]. Hypokalemia may be suspected in cases of muscle cramps. Another sneaky adverse effect of diuretics is hyponatremia, which is more common in older women after extended use of the medication. Acute gouty arthritis may result from the dose-dependent impact known as hyperuricemia. NOD (New Onset Diabetes) risk is increased by diuretics. ACE medications, angiotensin receptor blockers, calcium channel blockers, and placebo were all linked to a

substantially lower incidence of NOD than diuretics in a network meta-analysis of 22 clinical studies [45]. Between diuretics and b-blockers, there was no difference in the risk of NOD.

Diuretics use in Autism

Several symptoms of autism in children are improved by a medication that is often used to speed up urination, according to a small clinical trial that was published today in *Translational Psychiatry*. Autism is a neurodevelopmental illness that is characterised by poor social interaction and communication in afflicted individuals as well as repetitive behaviours. Autism is associated with altered GABA signalling, a neurotransmitter that typically reduces neural activity, according to research. And that elevated chloride ion concentrations in the brain cells are the cause of this disturbance of GABA. Yehezkel Ben-Ari, a neuroscientist at the Mediterranean Institute of Neurobiology, proposed that lowering these chloride ion levels might aid in treating the illness. In 2010, Ben-Ari and his co-author published a study in which they found that a three-month course of bumetanide, a diuretic that reduces chloride ions by preventing their entrance into cells, lowered autistic behaviour in five newborns without having any negative side effects [47].

Figure 1. Uses of Diuretics in different complications of body

CONCLUSION

In the present, diuretics are still a viable choice for treating edoema, congestive heart failure, cirrhosis, autism, toxemia. The majority of individuals can benefit from starting their treatment with diuretics. Instead, they concur that, in the case of hypertension, "The emphasis on first-choice drugs is outdated, given the predominant role of combination therapy," and that the choice should be made in accordance with the clinical circumstances of the individual patient.

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